
MANAGEMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SERVICES IN DIGITAL LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

Management of Library and Information Services is the work of careful planning which effects casting, planning, directing, organizing and controlling successfully done with the help of digital technologies. This paper discusses and emphasizes the need of the adaption of evolved management approach by the library and librarian using new information technology to provide the best information services to the user. This paper also suggests that how digital libraries can be effectively managed using digital information resources such as digital archives, e-books, digital collections, storing video, databases and all digital applications.

Keywords: *Digital library, Management, CAS, SDI, Circulation, Media integration technology, Library professionals*

Introduction:

Due to rapid advances in information technologies the management of library and information services changing effectively and fastly with changing nature of traditional libraries to digital libraries. Besides the development in information technologies, information systems and information networks have been developing. Digital libraries are playing the determined role to provide digital base services with managing a unique information environment. Digital libraries themselves redesign their services of information products managing their services to satisfy the changing information needs of the user community. The management of traditional libraries was totally different those today's digital libraries. Digital libraries are also procuring and new resources. Digital libraries are playing a vital role in today's

digital learning age. A digital library that deals with born data and the data to be digitized forum their analogue form. In this environment management of library and information services with the main function of digitization have to perform important activities such as access to digital contents faster information retrieval enhancing document delivery capabilities copyright clearness of right management, quality assessment, metadata design, delivery and long-term preservation.

This management depends on advanced digital technologies to deal with such tools. Library professionals and the staff involved in the management of library and information services in digital libraries should have undergone orientation programs and training are different levels to enhance their staff to do better work to render marked services to user's communities in the fully digital

environment. Media integration technology can be used to collect and maintain large data and different forms of information. To perform and managing library of information services can be carried out by coordination and management with the help of well-trained library professionals well equipped with advanced digital solutions.

Library and Information services rendered by Digital Library:

1. Web-based Services
2. CAS, SDI Services
3. Search Engine Services
4. Personalized Services
5. Co-operative Digital Library Services
6. Digital Archives

The management regarding library and information services in digital libraries the librarian, the information managers and library staff should know –

1. The terms and concepts, used in digital libraries to provide information in digital form.
2. Well trained and skilled to handle digital information dealing with digital information equipment's and location.
3. Familiar with correct evolution selection of databases and rendering services particularly in digital formats.
4. The staff to distinguished regarding databases, data collection and e-formats.
5. Planning, budgeting for successive management in digital libraries.
6. Should be familiar with copyright acts and developments in this field and guideline delivered on time to time for digital information services.

7. Effective and permissible use of documents and authentic databases and information sources.
8. Collection, sharing digitally with proper permission.
9. Creating local digital resources for searchable access.

Management of Library and Information Services in Digital Form:

Libraries and library professionals have also come up with digitization staffs, in this process printed resources of the library have to convert to digital resources using different recently increased applicable computer software and other computing devices. Some researchers like Hashmi and Mokhter (2012) study their issue regarding the requirement and preparing a new era for librarians in the digital age. In their research, they pointed out that for the digitization and use to society those new to the growth of electronics resources. It is important that the new era library professionals should be skilled in networking and will be helpful to society some important services can be performed with automated types of equipment and library activities for –

1) Circulation:

This can be easy by using advanced library management systems software's import jobs in the with library services and involves circulation. The librarian would be responsible for developing policy and procedures dealing with & analyzing strata reports with the help of standard and innovated digital software's.

2) Serial Control:

Serial control is a very important and most complicated function of the library. This function includes all organs of

library sections. Library and library supporting staff are directly involved to perform this function at the different levels they have to deal with all various stages. Generation of indexing databases, handling e-databases, and e-journals in serial control are automated serial control can be managed with some developed software such as soft lib software. There are different problems and difficulties but can be minimized with skilled staff with developed serial control software.

3) **Web Information Services:**

Due to technological advancements, web services include software, application, web protocols and data messaging which are centred exchange systems. Web services support and involve SOAP, USDL, XML, HTML all this developed technologies are being used in digital libraries. Library content in the form of digital form available library web portals, digital libraries incorporate all this services with one modules. Present-day libraries are using facebook and other social media platform for their students or users to expand library service coverage with digital equipment's and modules over the internet.

4) **SDI/CAS:**

In this digital age for the Selective Dissemination of Information and Current Awareness Service digital libraries are adapting recently developed electronic resources to provide electronic-based services for SDI and CAS social networking platforms and email, virtual

reference desk, chat rooms are being used. Librarian and library professionals are abided to provide SDI and CAS to the uses minimizing and using the advanced tools and techniques in digitization to save the time of the users.

5) **OPAC:**

The latest development in computer evolution OPAC is considered very important digital resources in the digital library to the users. Generally OPAC consist of simple index of the bibliographic data stored and located in the computer system and available online connectivity and quickly to the uses. OPAC is connected directly to the circulation system in farming users regarding the availability and location of the reading article. New users are able to search materials held by a particular library electronically as it is part of digital library.

Challenges in the Management of Library & Information Services in Digital Libraries:

Library professionals facing many challenges in digital library while managing digital collection.

The following challenges are identified in digital library providing information services such as – Retrieving digital information, Rights management and Access control, Network problem and skilled, Presentation problem and well trained professionals.

Conclusion:

Managing library and information services in the digital library has brought revolutionary changes. Library and

information science professionals are expected to update their skills to provide improved library services for users satisfaction for the success in digitization process librarians and library professionals working in digital environment have to acquire the required state of the art skill manage effectively in the digital library.

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